

Analysis of patient pathways in acute stroke care episodes

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Abstract: We analyzed the practices of acute stroke referral based on the data store of the National Health Development Institute in the 8-year-long period between 2010 and 2017. The essence of the method lies in the classification of cases and events, forming episodes of 8 distinct types, finding the de facto dominant care regions of the providers, and characterizing the care practices of the providers with the relative frequency of the various episode types.

The analysis highlighted some interesting spatial and provider related anomalies. There are remarkable, even an order of magnitude differences in the relative frequency of various event and episode types. An even more remarkable result is the formation of spatial patches of postal code areas with outlier values, on the relative frequency maps.

Some of the anomalies identified may be caused by the shortcomings of the current national case reporting and coding system. Any qualitative conclusions regarding the care system should be stated, however, after a more elaborate statistical analysis in the future.

Introduction

Public health care is a complex system which is very hard to comprehend by an intuitive or heuristic approach. Yet the standard data analysis tools and methods, routinely applied in any other industries, are very seldom applied in the field of health care planning and analysis in Hungary. The data store of the National Health Development Institute holds valuable data of every publicly financed case for more than two decades back by now, however, this data store has not been exploited for research until lately. In order for such an effort to be successful, it is imperative to understand the medical context and consider the current coding practices.

This paper presents the first results of a patient pathway analysis effort coordinated by the National Institute of Clinical Neurosciences in the field of acute stroke care. The main objective is to explore characteristics of the care

system, with a special respect to the spatial anomalies, the conformance to the applicable medical protocols [1] and the effect exerted by the specialized stroke care centers on the care network [2]. To our best knowledge, such an analysis has not yet been performed yet in the field of stroke care.

Data Sources

The anonymized case reports were queried from the Health Data Store of the National Healthcare Services Center and from the CT Register and complemented from various public sources. We defined acute stroke cases as cases associated with ICD codes I63 or I66 (acute ischemic stroke) as a main diagnosis, commencing between 1 January 2010 and 31 December 2017 and which had a CT performed in the -1..+7 day interval of the case onset date. This latter requirement was used to exclude the several cases (in fact two-third of all reported cases) which carried an acute stroke main diagnosis only for case financing reasons. The number of eligible cases was 281,948 belonging to 228,751 distinct patients. The yearly case number was ca. 32,000. We do not detail here the positive trends in the case numbers in the last decade.

Data cleaning was a complex process. We tracked down the known care provider mergers, new and closed up providers in the period to determine the set of valid care providers. Cases of patients whose gender, age or postal code area was impossible to determine were excluded from the study, as well as cases and procedures whose provider was unknown.

Methods

The methodology that we used for the patient pathway analysis was originally developed for analyzing ischemic heart disease episodes at the Medical Informatics Research and Development Center at the University of Pannonia [3]. The essence of the method is the formation of basic ‘care events’ based on case reports, and then episodes as a sequence of events that belong to the same patient and obey certain rules. Episodes are then classified according to their structure.

The event types we used included the skull CT, thrombolysis (TL), thrombectomy (TE) and basic care event (i.e. one without any invasive procedure or CT), denoted by EL. A CT is normally needed to assess the severity or nature of the stroke, and definitely needed before any TL/TE. We analyzed the spatial distribution of the various event types. We defined the maximal duration of an episode as 2 (5) days (5 for follow-up TL/TE events),

preceded by at least 1 event free day. Then we determined the *de facto* dominant regions of care for each stroke center according to the following procedure:

- For each postal code area, each episode gives one vote for the primary care provider of the episode. The *de facto* dominant care provider of the area is then selected as the one with the most votes.
- In case of a tie and if there was not a single episode in a postal code area, we select the closest provider, measured in time needed to reach the provider from the area by road, as the *de facto* dominant care provider of the area.

We classified the episodes according to their event sequences as follows.

- EL: an episode without CT, no further referral to another provider, no procedure performed
- CT: CT performed, no further referral to another provider, no procedure performed
- CT(TL/TE): CT and TL or TE performed, no further referral to another provider
- EL->CT: no CT at the first provider, the case is referred to another provider which performs a CT but no TL/TE
- EL->CT(TL/TE): no CT at the first provider, the case is referred to another provider which performs CT and TL/TE
- CT->CT: CT at the first provider, then the case is referred to another provider which performs a CT but no TL/TE
- CT->CT(TL/TE): CT at the first provider, then the case is referred to another provider which performs CT and TL/TE
- CT->TL/TE: CT at the first provider, then the case is referred to another provider which performs a TL/TE

Finally, the care practice of the providers was characterized by the spectra of the episodes that occurred in their region [4].

Results

We observed considerable differences in the spatial distribution of the cases. Considering only POSTAL CODE areas with a population over 1,000 for the whole 8-year-long period the minimum/maximum/average yearly case number per 1000 inhabitants was 0.96, 9.96 and 3.76, respectively, with a standard deviation of 1.19, which means that there are more than an order of

magnitude differences among areas with respect to the reported case numbers.

The event classification process yielded 282,229 events of type CT, 272,243 of EL, 11,743 of TL and 708 of TE that we could assign to an episode. The number of episodes by episode types was 220,061 for the CT type, 21,983 for EL, 15,610 for EL->CT, 10,974 for CT(TL/TE), 1,613 for CT->CT and 569 for CT->CT(TL/TE) i.e. in the vast majority of cases the care process involves a CT examination but no TL/TE procedure. This may be due to the nature of the stroke case or a time delay in the process which renders these procedures irrelevant.

We analyzed the spatial distribution of each episode type and found that it is in most cases quite inhomogeneous, with large distinguished, contiguous patches. For an example of this phenomenon see the three map sections below showing the central part of the country, with the episode numbers per 1,000 inhabitants for the CT (left), EL (middle) and EL->CT (right) episode types.

The maps show a vertical patch along the river Danube, of postal code areas with outlier values. This area is characterized by light shades i.e. low numbers of on-site CT (the expected protocol) and dark shades i.e. many cases of transporting the patient to another provider for CT. These altogether can be a sign of care logistics problems in the area. The maps do not show postal code areas with less than 1,000 inhabitants to improve statistical reliability.

The next map shows the *de facto* dominant practice regions of the specialized stroke clinics computed by the episode voting scheme. White means no episode, gray means a tie in the postal code area.

The regions are quite compact which is in line with our expectations following from the emergency nature of acute stroke care.

For each center, we computed the relative frequency of the 8 distinct episode types and performed a clustering procedure with these 8 ratios as cluster attributes. The result was that although there are considerable differences among the centers with respect to the frequency, no meaningful clusters could be formed, showing a homogeneous care practice across the country.

For more details on the results of the analysis, see [5].

Discussion

The most important result of the study was the identification of the spatial anomalies of the various episode types. There are remarkable, over an order of magnitude differences among postal code areas, but even more remarkable is how the outlier areas group together in *patches* in several cases. Since we used no geographical features for classifying the episodes, any clear and large outlier patches on these maps—which patches are to be found on virtually all the maps—mark a spatial anomaly of the stroke care system.

Another important conclusion of the study is the characterization of the care providers with their episode type frequencies as the ‘care spectrum’ of the provider. As a result, we identified some outlier centers that may need further investigation, or per case studies to find the causes of their practices.

The goal of this analysis was limited to the exploration of stroke care related data. Any qualitative statements regarding the care system must be formed and proven by statistical methods. This is a field for future research.

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